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Blurry Access: A Bibliographic Analysis of Transparency Literature

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Introduction

Transparency is a central topic in the political science, administration studies and governance literature. Over time the literature on this topic has profited from a diverse set of approaches stemming from a wide array of fields, notwithstanding conceptual inconsistencies and lax definitional groundings (Hood, 2010). From corruption curbing potential to local fiscal administration tools (Brusca et al., 2018), emphases have moved beyond the national scope in order to analyse the more specific and dynamic interactions at the local and international levels (Bjurulf & Elgström, 2004).

We look at these dynamics from a bibliographic perspective; that is, not only focusing on the subject-specific research, but looking at a broader picture determined by referencing, clustering and funding issues. We pay particular attention to the knowledge exchange factors therein, specifically through collaborations and funding.

A sample of 242 publications on the topic of transparency is thus analysed, in a period of 36 years (1984-2020), looking at the thematic and methodological evolution. Our analysis focuses largely on bibliographic data which we analyse in the form of networks of citations and geographic relations. Additionally, we study the effect of open access publishing within our sample and engage it from a funding-based perspective, identifying the trends in publication practices. In doing so, we hope to emphasise the non-trivial role that knowledge diffusion plays in understanding and shifting paradigms, with special attention to the case of institutional arrangements – such as transparency.

We conclude that, from our sample, transparency has been largely studied from the so-called Global North, with large disparities regarding open access publishing and funding availability, limiting the very access to the publications in relation to scholars in the so-called Global South.

Materials and Methods

In a similar vein as Cucciniello et al. (2017) this bibliographic analysis of the literature looks to advance the understanding in the field of transparency, yet – following Chen and Song (2017) as well as Sugimoto and Larivière (2018) – it looks to highlight the role of research data and metadata for the broader comprehension of underlying or structural issues. We follow-up on Liberati et al.’s (2009) framework for meta analyses and literature reviews;

namely, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Statement (PRISMA). We undertake a modified version of the protocol and reiterate two intermediate stages aided by an unsupervised machine learning approach, in what we call an iterative PRISMA methodology. Table 1 summarises the coding criteria for the final sample.

Table 1. Coding Criteria

Criterion	Remarks
Author, Year, Title, Keywords, Publication	Primary bibliographic information to be accounted for every work.
Field of Study	Secondary bibliographic information characterising the multi- and interdisciplinary approaches to the study of transparency.
Methodological Design	Differentiation between theoretical and empirical studies.
Geographic Representation	This criterion allows for a sub-categorisation of transparency research into spatial units (countries or regions).
Author Affiliation	In complement to the above criterion, author affiliation is the disaggregated unit that sheds light into the closest geographic attributes of knowledge dynamics. Affiliation is split correspondingly as per the number of co-authors and counted individually – that is, one affiliation count per counted author.
Funding Acknowledgement	Here only third party funding is considered as to highlight the role of patron-type financial support that sponsors scientific production – in contrast, this shows how many works are done and published out of regular research activities in universities, think tanks and/or civil society organisations.
Access Type	Here we categorise access in three broad types; namely, 1) Open Access, 2) Hybrid Access and 3) Closed Access. In identifying only these broad categories we choose to group the sub-types of open and hybrid access modes (e.g., Gold, Green, Bronze) into two categories (open = Gold, everything else = Hybrid), while also grouping all other types with unspecified access data under the closed access category.
References Cited	We look at these in order to analyse citation and co-citation relations between authors and/or groups of authors and problematise the, usually, closed networks that characterise academic production.

With this approach we queried the CrossRef and Scopus databases through their APIs and conducted a manual search of the Web of Science (WoS) database¹ and obtained an initial sample of over 3000 records, which was partly complemented by a small subset of pre-

¹The final query included the terms "transparency", "accountability", "government", "corruption", "open", "democracy", "power", "society", "civil", "management", "administration", "policy", "international", "local", "state", "public", "service", "trust" – thus covering a progressively narrow set of matches. The query sequence was expanded with each call; so, the addition of new terms signifies the use of the boolean operator "AND" thus limiting the matches returned.

selected influential documents (four books from highly cited authors in the field).² The final number of 242 works (articles, books, and book chapters) was narrowed down through the use of the *fulltext* and *topicmodels* packages in the R programming framework (Chamberlain, 2021; Grün & Hornik, 2011). With this approach, repeated Application Programming Interface (API) queries were automated and conducted in intervals, connecting directly with repositories through the R interface and later screened and filtered with a topic modelling approach (LDA). VosViewer (v.1.16.17) and Gephi (v.0.9.2) were complementarily used in the network analyses and visualisation.

LDA and Topic Classification

The LDA modelling function searches text structures and calculates, among others, proximity and probability – i.e. the probability of finding the same terms in or across documents (for full detail see Blei et al., 2003). Methodologically speaking, terms are words and documents are the collected works (articles and book chapters, for example). The model groups the texts and separates them into documents and finds the most relevant terms, in and across documents – the process is iterated until a pre-defined number of topics is fitted. That is, the most probable distribution of terms per topic is calculated and grouped, signalling some structural connection.

Results

We programmed the LDA function to estimate and cluster six topics based on this probabilistic assignment. Our topics, then, are listed with their corresponding five principal (exclusive) associated terms in Table 2.

Table 2. LDA Topics with Top 5 Terms

Topic	Terms
National Government	County; Measure; Fiscal; Model; Govern
Local Government	Municipal; Local Government; Indices; Regard; Differ
Open Government	Open; Develop; Portal; e-Government; Research
Corruption	Corrupt; Effect; Trust; Organ; People
Institutions	State; Policy; Polit*; Institute; Administrator
International Organisation	Report; EITI**; Govern; Company; Country

Notes; */ The word-stem “Polit” refers to a number of associated terms (e.g., political, politics).

**/ Acronym for the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative.

Regional Distribution of Academic Production

Figure 1 complements our thoughts regarding a delicate (un)balance in the academic production landscape is underpinned by a dependent interrelation in the way knowledge is disseminated, and clearly display the regional distribution of academic output dependent on two characteristics; namely, the authors’ affiliation and the publications’ case study or

² The platform <https://www.connectedpapers.com> was used to qualitatively identify these works.

regional focus. In other words, where the authors are speaking from and what (analytically coded as where) are they speaking about.³

We thus identify a clear Eurocentric pattern that, despite our best efforts at controlling for over-representation in the sample, is a notorious source of distortion. In line with our previous ideas, we find grounds to further ponder on the notion that this output inequality boosts the changing topic (or thematic) foci in the scholarship by means of academic postcolonial structures (Connell et al., 2017). That is, as Europe and the United States (USA) move beyond over-populated fields (e.g., national governance and institutionalism) towards other *novel* approaches to transparency and accountability, particularly in the scope of the locality and regionalism, countries of the so-called Global South *catch up* to these fields and scholars replicate or conduct alternative versions of existing theoretical or empirical models.

Figure 1. Authors' Affiliations and Regional Distribution of Studies

Networked Scholarship

One issue, however, that the data we have gathered allows us to analyse and visualise is the networked dynamic underlying the published documents. As in any social interrelation, academic publishing is nurtured by constant and critical exchanges. These exchanges take the form of informed opinions, expansions upon previous theories or theorems, and qualitative or quantitative proof of some hypothesis. What has remained to some extent unclear in the academic landscape is the role that networked social capital works. In other words, how do personal or institutional relations impact the dynamic of knowledge production (e.g., Chen & Song, 2017, pp. 11–12).

³ The regional distribution is based on the categories used in the Quality of Government Standard Dataset (QoG) but grouped so as to avoid individual cases (Teorell et al., 2022).

It has been limitedly problematised, as it has been also failed to indicate whether top publishing scholars make use of their social capital (in the typical sense of the term, see Bourdieu & Wacquant, 1992; also expanded upon by Rothstein, 2011) in order to achieve a greater dissemination of their works. Of course, to insinuate foul play in the academic circles would be a tedious and too great of an argument – one, that is, that surpasses the scope of this article. In that sense, and on a needed methodological note, the Figure 2 only shows how these connections are structured (though it will be based on a smaller sample of the documents, specifically 213 documents – all of them journal articles – for which citation and other metadata were available in a structured format).⁴ This network was visualised, and calculated, using the Fruchterman-Reingold (1991) layout, best used to emphasise complementarities in networks (Gephi.org, n.d.) due to its regular and system-like display.

Such a citation network like in Figure 2 is determined by three variables; namely, thematic clusters, interrelation between authors/works and overall author degree. The latter is determined by a simple average of the number of connections (edges) from one author (node) to another. The former two are better characterised by measures of density and modularity, which characterise the actual connections within a network based on the potential ones.

This particular visualisation stresses the fact that there may indeed be clusters or communities of scholars mutually reciprocating their citations based on geographical proximity, affiliations or simply thematic affinity. For example, scholars researching local governance (orange, upper-left sector), more theory driven works (light blue, middle sector), as well as case-centred studies (purple, lower-left and dark green, right-most sectors).

In this sense, this author-to-author citation network is moderately modular (a 0.43 estimated value) with six community sub-structures in the network. Again, colour-coded, the groupings reveal an even more interconnected landscape. Unsurprisingly, the average degree value for each node is 6.9 (as the network includes all cited works in every work in the sample), meaning that each node has, in average, close to seven connections to other nodes.

Open Access Literature

In order to make publications even more accessible to a wider audience, calls have been made in recent years to open up not only the final access of the published materials, but also the process of submission and review (Miedema, 2022; Prager et al., 2019; Wicherts, 2016). However, here we only focus on the final part of the process, where some of the geographic and systemic conditions still hold.

We systematised the funding information for every publication and looked for explicit information regarding the source(s) of funds directed specifically to the undertaking, publishing and dissemination of the works. As per common practice, this information is found in two sections; under a specific Funding header or, lacking the former, under the Acknowledgements header. Our experience in this systematisation shows that there is no clear or unique standard for which to code such information (see Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018, p. 110). On a methodological note, we must highlight the fact that for this analysis, we do use the entire sample (242 publications).

⁴Although references were collected for every document, the technical challenge of formatting these to the standard needed for their input into VosViewer and/or Gephi made us decide for the WoS output format. Thus, despite the availability of DOIs and or publication names for every document, 26 of them were excluded since the WoS advanced search could not find the metadata needed. Further, through the intermediate step with VosViewer, the sample was again reduced as to show only the most relevant nodes (documents) citation-wise.

Figure 2. Citation Network

Thus, Figure 3 condenses these two sources of information and projects them in a way that follows a similar narrative to our overall perspective; that is, presenting the geographic dimension interlinked with the more material elements of access and funding. A greater proportion of the works in our sample has a hybrid access. However, in relation to open vs closed access, the number of publications without OA is also larger. Hybrid access imbricates all intermediate and non-all gold OA formats.

Regarding the source of funding, contrasting the explicit mention of third-party funding, institutional affiliation funding assumes that scholars publish their research as part of their academic duties, and that no additional funds have been dedicated to this end. Visually, a large majority of the works fall under the institutional affiliation category, signalling an overall lack of external funding for research in the transparency field.

This pattern could signify that no structural incentive exists to publish in OA, vis-a-vis higher costs associated with OA (Jahn et al., 2021). Also, it could signify that externally funded research is published without OA requirements, which goes against recent guidelines for the

promotion of academic and scientific production (Brugger, 2020; European Commission, 2021; Kowaltowski et al., 2021). Not only is this phenomenon detrimental to the overall academic divulgation of knowledge, but falls in clear contradiction to our implied topic-as-a-medium outlook.

Figure 3. Open Access and Funding Details of the Literature

Discussion

Our analysis has shown that there are at least two problematic trends that need to be addressed in a comprehensive manner pertaining the dynamics of academic publishing. Firstly, we follow Bellis (2009) and Chen and Song (2017) in the problematisation of academic outputs as part of a larger process of knowledge production and diffusion. This is guided by the number of references all other works mention, signalling some centrality in the field (Figure 2). This is compounded by the also latent geographic divide in the knowledge production (figures 1 and 3).

Our data prohibits us of making larger statements on the matter, but we can devise informed assumptions regarding the dynamics characterising the transparency academic landscape in regard to how (un)evenly distributed the academic interrelation and production networks seem to be. This is one central theme in Sugimoto and Larivière's (2018) perspective, which is taken up from a more critical and focused outlook by Collyer (2018), Connell et al. (2017) and Alatas (2003). This creates sub-communities that are characterised for their enclosed nature, with little cooperative work to the outside (international institutes or universities) and heavily theme-oriented. This has potential consequences that, presumably, have been taken as a normal behaviour, such as brain-draining from scholars in the so-called Global South and, consequently, an over-representation of research output from the so-called Global North.

This unbalanced state of scholarly inquiry seems to be also heavily affected by structural factors that materially create possibility-gaps for researchers (Lane et al., 2014). For example, “funding typically attributes resources (or credit for funding) to principal investigators, and obliterates the increasingly collaborative nature of funded research” (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018, p.111). That is, financial means play a part in the highly segmented landscape of research in transparency, since the elite scholars (those central authors identified in the networked visualisation) contribute with only a close circle of colleagues based on thematic and geographic proximity and, when international cooperation occurs, funding schemes favour the renowned scholars, usually, in the so-called Global North.

Conclusions

This review of the transparency literature has shown the evolution of the field through the prism of bibliographic and methodological data. In doing so, we have shed light into underlying disparities that go in line with arguments of structural problems and historical relations in socio-political contexts Collyer (2018). We have highlighted the irony of the field in researching a topic that, due to determinants beyond the control of scholars (though OA policies may slowly generate a structural change), is in itself little transparent. The blurriness of the state of research in transparency and accountability helps us to address the overall debate of academic production in a critical manner, engaging with issues such as publishing and funding. These latter elements should suppose gateways for a wider diffusion of knowledge, yet they have seem to function as gatekeepers, undermining the duality we argue about – transparency as object and as medium. Though the first one may be well-developed and methodologically rich, the second one remains blurry in regard to the way knowledge is distributed.

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